

Academic Adjustment Problems and Helpfulness of Supervision, Guidance and Counseling Services among Undergraduate Students at Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi, Pathum Thani Province, Thailand

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Abstract— *The purposes of this study were to find the academic adjustment problems faced by undergraduate students; to determine the helpfulness of guidance and counseling services with students' academic adjustment problems; and to interview lecturers on how they do provide supervision and guidance to help undergraduate students who challenged academic adjustment problems. This study was done at Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi, Pathum Tani Province, Thailand by using Mooney Problem Checklist, College Form and applying the Guidance and Counseling Services. For this study sample was 240 randomly selected undergraduate students from eight difference faculties and for qualitative study of procedures for supervision, guidance and counseling six lecturers (3 males and 3 females) were interviewed. This study observed that as per Mooney (1950)'s Problem Check List majority of students had experience one or the other type of problem on this ten item scale. Maximum problem was found ' Not know how to study effectively' in 92.5%, 219 (91.25%) students easily distracted from their schools' work, 206 (85.83%) students were not planning their schools' work ahead, 197 (82.08%) students were having a poor background for some subjects, 190 (79.17%) students were inadequate high school training, 167 (69.58%) students were forgetting things they have earned in school, 166 (69.17%) students were getting low grades, 163 (67.92%) students were not spending enough time in study, 156 (65.00%) students were not getting studied done on time and 153 (63.75%) of them were unable to concentrate well. 92.92% students agreed with the helpfulness of guidance and counseling services. On further analysis on Chi-square test significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher proportion of students were agreed on helpfulness of counselling and guidance on ever scale studied. Six lecturers in this study claimed that they provided the responsibilities for the roles of supervision and supporting students with guidance and counseling services when they faced academic adjustment problems.*

Keywords: *Academic Adjustment Problems, Supervision, Guidance and Counseling Services.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Academic adjustment is included to life satisfaction, academic performance and psychosocial emotional balance among students. Academic adjustment related to another terms of adjustment such as home/family adjustment, health adjustment, social adjustment, and emotional adjustment. Undergraduate students adjusted their academic problems by adapting the experiment with new found freedom and responsibilities.¹

Academic adjustment problems were found among students who were being away from home, family and friends for the first time and feeling homesickness. It changes their life by altered living arrange or living in dormitory, felt difficulties with socializing or making friends, completed to new environment or differed in social network, managed difficult time and studied skills, difficult adjusted to university

classes and accompanied workload etc had health problems and confused career direction.² Academic adjustments problems among undergraduate students in universities of US, Malaysia, Japan, India etc, influence academic performance of students.³

Undergraduate students are facing their academic adjustment problems because they are lacking the guidance and counselling services to help them to cope with their academic adjustment problems.

This study was conducted with the aim to find out academic problems of students and the helpfulness of guidance and counselling services with following objectives:-

1. To find out the academic adjustment problems faced by Thai undergraduate students.
2. To determine the helpfulness of guidance and counselling services in helping undergraduate students to cope with their academic adjustment problems
3. To identify the responsibilities of the lecturers providing supervision and guidance for undergraduate students who faced academic adjustment problems

II. METHODOLOGY

This cross sectional sequential explanatory study was conducted to find out the academic adjustment problems faced by Thai undergraduate students and to determine the helpfulness of guidance and counselling services in helping undergraduate students to cope with their academic adjustment problems. This study was conducted at Rajamagala University of Technology Thanyaburi, Pathum Tani Province, Thailand in year 2018.

This study was done by using Mooney Problem Checklist, College Form and applying the Guidance and Counseling Services. Study sample was 240 randomly selected undergraduate students from eight difference faculties. And for qualitative study of procedures for supervision, guidance and counseling six lecturers (3 males and 3 females) were interviewed on how they have provided supervision and guidance to help undergraduate students who challenged academic adjustment problems.

The quantitative data is collected and analysed in the initial stage of the research, followed by the collection and analysis of qualitative data

2.1 Population and Samples

The population for this study was 240 randomly selected students by gender and year level as shown in Table 1. From the second year students, 40 (16.67%) were males and 40 (16.66%) were females. Likewise, the randomly selected student samples of third year consisted of 40 (16.66%) males and 40 (16.67%) females and from fourth year students, 40 (16.67%) were males and 40 (16.67%) were females.

Table 1
Study population of the study

Gender	Undergraduate Student Samples			
	2nd Year	3 rd Year	4th Year	Total
Male	40 (16.67%)	40 (16.67%)	40 (16.67%)	120 (50.00%)
Female	40 (16.67%)	40 (16.67%)	40 (16.67%)	120 (50.00%)
Total	80 (33.33%)	80 (33.33%)	80 (33.34%)	240 (100.00%)

2.2 The Instruments used are Mooney Problem Checklist, College Form (Mooney, 1950)⁴ and the six scales of guidance and counselling service (See, 1996)⁵ translated into Thai language.

Statistical Analysis: Data were compiled and statistically analyzed by using Microsoft excel 2010 worksheet. Results were expressed in percentages and proportion. Chi-square was used to find out significance of difference in proportion. For significance p value less than 0.05 was considered significant.

III. RESULTS

In present study, it was observed that as per Mooney (1950)'s Problem Check List majority of students had experience one or the other type of problem on this ten item scale. Maximum problem was found 'Not know how to study effectively' in 92.5%, 219 (91.25%) students easily distracted from their schools' work, 206 (85.83%) students were not planning their schools' work ahead, 197 (82.08%) students were having a poor background for some subjects, 190 (79.17%) students were inadequate high school training, 167 (69.58%) students were forgetting things they have earned in school, 166 (69.17%) students were getting low grades, 163 (67.92%) students were not spending enough time in study, 156 (65.00%) students were not getting studied done on time and 153 (63.75%) of them were unable to concentrate well. (Table 2)

Table 2
Academic Adjustment Problems of study population as per Mooney Problem Check List (N = 240)

S. No.	Items	Yes		No	
		Number	%	Number	%
1	Not know how to study effectively	222	92.50	18	7.50
2	Easily distracted from my school's work	219	91.25	21	8.75
3	Not panning my school's work ahead	206	85.83	34	14.17
4	Having a poor background for some subjects	197	82.08	43	17.92
5	Inadequate high school training	190	79.17	50	20.83
6	Forgetting things I've learned in school	167	69.58	73	30.42
7	Getting low grades	166	69.17	74	30.83
8	Not spending enough time in study	163	67.92	77	32.08
9	Not getting studies done on time	156	65.00	84	35.00
10	Unable to concentrate well	153	63.75	87	36.25

When effectiveness of six item scale for counselling and guidance was observed it was found that majority (more than 77.08%) of students were in opinion about its helpfulness, 92.92% student were in opinion of helpfulness of Individual and Group Counselling, 79.17% student were in opinion of helpfulness of 'Consultation', 78.33% student were in opinion of helpfulness of 'Guidance', 85.42% student were in opinion of helpfulness of 'Coordination', 76.25% student were in opinion of helpfulness in 'Assessment' and 77.08% student were in opinion of helpfulness in 'Personal Growth and Development. On further analysis on Chi-square test significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher proportion of students were agreed on helpfulness of counselling and guidance on ever scale studied. (Table 3)

Table 3
Helpfulness of counselling and guidance of Scale (See, 1996)⁶ to the students (N=240)

S. No.	Scale	Yes	No	Chi-square Test at 1 DF	P Value LS
		Number (%)	Number (%)		
1	Individual and Group Counselling	223 (92.92)	17 (7.08)	350.208	<0.001 S
2	Consultation	190 (79.17)	50 (20.83)	161.008	<0.001 S
3	Guidance	188 (78.33)	52 (21.67)	151.875	<0.001 S
4	Coordination	205 (85.42)	35 (14.58)	238.008	<0.001 S
5	Assessment	183 (76.25)	57 (23.75)	130.208	<0.001 S
6	Personal Growth and Development	185 (77.08)	55 (22.92)	138.675	<0.001 S

To find out sense of responsibilities of the lecturer providing supervision and guidance and counselling services to help students with academic adjustment problems, the interviews were used to answer this research question. From the interview with six lectures, three of them said that they provided individual and group counselling services to students. They narrated as follows:-

Respondent first (R1): *“I helped with an individual student to deal with academic problems”*.

Respondent fifth (R5): *“I discussed with students who had academic problems individually class”*.

Respondent sixth (R6): *“I helped with group of students to deal with academic problems”*.

Three respondents said that they did their roles of supervision and guidance by providing consultation service to students. They narrated as follows:-

R1: *“I consulted with parents to help students increase the effectiveness in intervening and preventing of academic adjustment problems”*.

R3: *“I consulted with students’ personnel to help them increase the effectiveness in intervening and preventing of academic adjustment problems”*.

R4: *“I encouraged collaboration to provide professional expertise to advocate for individual and specific groups of students”*.

Three respondents said that they provided guidance services to students. They narrated as follows:-

R2: *“I promoted effective implementation of the guidance activities to solve students ‘academic adjustment problems”*.

R3: *“I managed guidance activities to help students with academic adjustment problems”*.

R4: *“I managed academic adjustment for students including students’ needs.”*.

Three respondents said that they provided coordination services to students. They narrated as follows:-

R1: *“I used an effective process when referring students to special programs and services to help students with academic adjustment problems”*.

R2: *"I coordinated with school by promoting on how to intervene and prevent with academic adjustment problems"*.

R5: *"I applied an effective process the special programs and services to help students with academic adjustment problems"*.

Three respondents said that they provided assessment services to students. They narrated as follows:-

R2: *"I assisted of school personnel and other assessment data to guide students with intervention problems, goal and plan"*.

R5: *"I enhanced schools' work of students' personnel in guiding student set goal by promoting understanding of standardized test results and other assessment concerning students with academic adjustment problems"*.

R6: *"I enhanced schools' work of students in guiding them to set plan by promoting and understanding of standardized test results"*.

Three respondents said they provided personal growth and development to students. They narrated as follows:-

R1: *"I informed students of possible information on the counselling for personal growth and development supporting students 'academic adjustment"*.

R4: *"I increased awareness of personal values, attitudes supporting students' academic adjustment."*

R6: *"I encouraged family to involve and understand their children when working with students in sensitive areas that might be controversial and effect to their academic adjustment"*

IV. DISCUSSION

In present study, it was observed that as per Mooney (1950)'s Problem Check List majority (92.5%) of students had experience one or the other type of problem on this ten item scale. Maximum problem was found 'Not know how to study effectively' in 92.5%, 219 (91.25%) students easily distracted from their schools' work, 206 (85.83%) students were not planning their schools' work ahead, 197 (82.08%) students were having a poor background for some subjects, 190 (79.17%) students were inadequate high school training, 167 (69.58%) students were forgetting things they have earned in school, 166 (69.17%) students were getting low grades, 163 (67.92%) students were not spending enough time in study, 156 (65.00%) students were not getting studied done on time, and 153 (63.75%) of them were unable to concentrate well.

Although Getu Belay⁶ reported adjustment disorder in students of Ethiopian University but other authors^{3,7,8} reported much more proportion of students with adjustment problems those are in somewhat in line of present study. Esmael et al³ reported prevalence of adjustment problem 30.1%. In Malaysia and North Jordan that was 42.8 and 50 percent of universities students having adjustment problems.^{7,8}

Brian Wilson⁹ also did a study on adjustment problems in a developing country on a representative sample of 242 first-year and 60 fourth-year students showed that there are problems which are sufficiently potent, general and/or persistent to be a cause for concern to the university authorities.

Sohrabi, R et al¹⁰ found Group Counselling Effectiveness in Solving adjustment problem and improving Educational Self-Efficacy.

V. CONCLUSION

Present study concludes that 92.5% of students have one and other adjustment problem and 92.92% students agreed with the helpfulness of guidance and counseling services. In addition, the findings of interviews' results found that lecturers provided supervision and guidance and counseling services to undergraduate students who faced academic adjustment problems.

There are practical recommendations are given to the four main sectors who are involved with undergraduate students as follows:-

Government should set up guidance and counseling cell to help students on academic adjustment problems (Topu & Aranep, 2014)¹¹.

University should decide to promote counseling and guidance services to students. for academic adjustment and coping abilities into all courses of the study. All people in educational faculty must have and provide services of guidance and counseling to support academic adjustment of students (Godelek & Kayar, 2012)¹².

Counselors/Lecturers should be needed to promote interpersonal awareness of counseling students, helped students in navigating challenging achievement-oriented and these tasks may be an important in the academic adjustment problems (Klibert, et al, 2014)¹³.

Parents might be used to improve the efficiency of parent training in guidance and counseling services to promote parent's awareness about the need of their child and to support their academic adjustment (Sohrabi, Mohamadadi, and Aghdam, 2013)¹⁰

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared till now.

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